

Colorimetric Method for Determination of Anthraquinone in Root of *Rheum Palaestinum* Feinbrun

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Abstract

This study aims to shed light on methods for determining the quantities of various anthraquinone derivatives mentioned in the pharmacopoeia of countries around the world. It also aims to determine the amount of anthraquinone derivatives in the roots of Palestinian rhubarb (*Rheum palaestinum* Feinbrun) using the colorimetric method provided by the State Pharmacopoeia of the USSR.

The results of a study to determine the amount of anthraquinone derivatives in Palestinian rhubarb roots using the colorimetric method showed that the roots contain (3.41%) of anthraquinone derivatives.

The results of the study showed that the colorimetric method is considered reliable, accurate, easy to implement, and inexpensive compared to other methods, but it is not suitable for determining the quantity of individual anthracene derivatives with sufficient accuracy.

Keywords: *Rheum palaestinum* Feinbrun, colorimetric method, anthraquinone derivatives

Introduction

More than 4,000 years have passed since the rhubarb genus's first recorded uses. In many nations throughout the world, traditional medicine makes extensive use of rhubarb. Over time, American and European medicine have also embraced this practice. Due to its unique composition—a combination of two categories of biologically active substances—anthracene derivatives and tannins—rhubarb is practically utilized in global practice, and its numerous species are actively used.

The rhubarb genus has an extremely rich base of active substances and there are many medicines based on it that have been approved by international medicine and documented in the pharmacopoeia of many countries of the world.

These results highlight the importance of studying the qualitative and quantitative chemical composition of the active substances, especially anthraquinone derivatives, as well as studying their biological effects on rhubarb.

Researchers used several methods to quantitatively determine anthraquinone derivatives. Some of these methods are mentioned in the International Pharmacopoeia, and some are documented in various researches and studies, the most famous of which are the following:

- The American Pharmacopoeia proposes to determine the content of anthraquinone derivatives in aloe leaves in terms of barbaloin, considering it equal to 240 at 512 nm. During the determination, the reduced forms of anthraquinone derivatives are converted into oxidized ones by heating their sum with iron (III) chloride in an acidic environment.
- The European and British Pharmacopoeia determine the amount of anthraquinone derivatives in buckthorn bark and a standardized dry extract using the standard substance (glucofrangulin A), using its specific absorbance at 515 nm. To enhance the color of anthraquinone derivatives, magnesium

acetate is used. The specific absorption index (Δ) of glucofrangulin A at 515 nm of a colored solution is 204.

- A method of spectrophotometry of water-alcohol extraction of raw materials at a wavelength of 510 nm in terms of frangula-emodin is proposed for the quantitative determination of the amount of anthracene derivatives in rhubarb roots in the State Pharmacopoeia of the Russian Federation, XIV edition FS.2.5.0092.18 "Roots of rhubarb palmate".
- The Republic of Belarus' Pharmacopoeia, which is based on the European Pharmacopoeia, suggests using spectrophotometry to quantitatively determine the amount of anthracene derivatives in terms of styzine and the amount of total hydroxyanthracene derivatives in terms of rhein.
- Homeopathic pharmacopoeias from Europe, Britain, Japan, and Germany refer to plants that yield raw rhubarb roots, including medicinal and tangut rhubarb, without distinguishing between qualitative and quantitative determination techniques.
- Thus, the European Pharmacopoeia and the British Pharmacopoeia follow the identical procedures, as previously mentioned. The German Homeopathic Pharmacopoeia suggests using the spectrophotometric approach to determine the amount of the sum of hydroxyanthracene derivatives in terms of rhein for the quantitative measurement of the method in the aforementioned pharmacopoeias.
- The Japanese Pharmacopoeia's techniques the peak area of sensoside A is determined quantitatively using high-performance liquid chromatography; a diluted acetic acid and acetonitrile (4:1) combination serves as the mobile phase.
- Anthraquinone derivatives can be determined with high accuracy by High-performance thin layer chromatography method HPTLC and high-performance liquid chromatographic method HPLC.
- Phenolic hydroxyls of anthraquinone derivatives have weak acidic properties, these properties are easier to use when dimethylformamide and dimethyl sulfoxide are used as solvents and the quantitative content is determined by acid-base titration, establishing the equivalence point potentiometrically with a platinum electrode, and using sodium hydroxide as a titrant.

In conclusion, we say that for the quantitative determination of anthraquinones in raw materials, many methods are used, such as Spectrophotometry, high-performance thin layer chromatography HPTLC, high-performance liquid chromatographic HPLC, acid-base titration, gravimetric, colorimetric, UV Spectrophotometry, Polarographic, voltammetric, Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy, Fiber optics reflectance spectroscopy, Mass spectrometry, Color spectrophotometry and methods.

We can conclude that rhubarb is used in global practice on an equal footing with other medicinal plants by examining the national pharmacopoeia of different countries. However, the techniques used in quantitative analysis are not consistent. The low use of modern analytical methods indicates their high cost and that the use of traditional methods in studying these plants to determine the amounts of active substances accumulated in them is better and cheaper and has the ability to conduct a more comprehensive investigation of their chemical composition, both qualitatively and quantitatively.

The purpose of the study is to determine the amount of anthraquinone derivatives in the roots of Palestinian rhubarb (*Rheum palaestinum* Feinbrun) using the colorimetric method provided by the State Pharmacopoeia of the USSR.

Materials and Methods

An uncommon species of plant in the Polygonaceae family is *Rheum palaestinum*. The plant is semi-perennial and grows to a height of 15–40 cm. The leaves are enormous, spherical, and have wrinkles on their 20–50 cm diameter surface. The blooms lack drama and are merely green. It yields broad-winged, triangular fruits. In Palestine, Jordan, and Syria's mountainous desert regions, it flourishes during the wet winter months. This plant is a wild species that goes by the names Ribas, Rhubarb, Attarfan, and Atravan in the local dialect. Its range include the southern region of Palestine and Sinai, with its primary habitats being the Syrian and Eastern deserts of Jordan.

Figure 1. Rheum palaestinum Feinbrun

Plant Material

Since we were unable to travel to the Negev region in Palestine in order to collect the required samples, we collected the roots of the Palestinian rhubarb plant in the month of June-July from the Bayer Valley region in the desert of southeastern Jordan. The roots were dried in the shade at 30°C. Next, grind it into a powder using a mortar and pestle. Finally, strain it through a sieve with a 0.16 mm diameter.

Methods

Quantitative determination of anthracene in the roots of Rheum palaestinum Feinbrun: The total anthraquinone content in the roots of Rheum palaestinum Feinbrun was determined using the colorimetric method provided by the State Pharmacopoeia of the USSR.

Previously, in another study by the author, a phytochemical study examined the antibacterial and antifungal activity of the leaves of the Palestinian rhubarb plant.

From the results of the previous study, it was found that the leaves contain a group of active substances, and the following compounds were identified and isolated: anthraquinones (chrysophanol), flavonoids (rutin, hyperoside, myricetin, and quercetin), hydroxycinnamic acids (caffeoyl, chlorogenic) and organic acids (citric, malic).

Microbiological studies conducted on the aqueous -alcoholic extract of Palestinian rhubarb leaves indicate the presence of antimicrobial activity, especially against Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922), spore cultures (*Bacillus subtilis*) and Antifungal activity especially against yeast-like fungi of the genus *Candida*. (White ATCC 885-653).

Results and Discussion

To standardize raw materials and preparations containing anthraquinone derivatives, the State Pharmacopoeia of the USSR in the 11th edition introduces the Otter Hoff method (colorimetric) [28].

Using this method, the amount of anthraquinones in rhubarb root is determined, the forms of glycosides and the amount of aglycones are determined and the concentration is calculated according to a titration table.

The mentioned method requires the use of salt $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a standard to construct a calibration graph from which the concentration of anthraquinone derivatives in the test object is found.

The colorimetric method is based on the Borntrager reaction, which consists in the fact that the oxidized forms of anthracene derivatives, when dissolved in alkalis, form a red color, and the reduced forms yellow. The reaction is positive for chrysacine anthraquinones. Anthrones, anthranols, dianthrones and their glycosides give a red color after hydrolysis and oxidation.

This method does not allow the determination of the quantity of individual anthracene derivatives with sufficient accuracy.

Quantitative phytochemical analysis of total Palestinian rhubarb roots for anthraquinone content: An analytical sample of rhubarb roots is crushed to particle size and passed through a sieve with holes of 0.16

mm. About 0.3 g of crushed raw place the material (roots) in a 100 ml beaker, add 7.5 ml of glacial acetic acid, and heat the mixture on water bath (at a low boil) for 15 minutes. And complete the process according to the method given in the State Pharmacopoeia of the USSR in the eleventh edition [28].

The content of anthracene derivatives in terms of istizine and dry raw materials in percent (X) is calculated using the formula:

$$X = \frac{C \times 250 \times 100 \times 100}{m (100 - W)},$$

Where:

C: is the content of anthracene derivatives in 1 ml of the colorimetric solution, found from the calibration graph, in grams;

m: is the mass of raw materials in grams;

W: is the weight loss when drying raw materials as a percentage.

The results obtained are presented in Table. 1.

Table 1: Content of anthracene derivatives in the roots of the Rheum palaestinum Feinbrun plant

Plant and parts	N ^o of experiments	m/g	C/g	W%	x,%	$\bar{x} \pm \Delta\bar{x}, \%$ n=5
Root of Rheum palaestinum Feinbrun	1	1,0075	0,140	13	3,48	3,41 ± 0,02
	2	1,0025	0,135		3,37	
	3	1,0032	0,136		3,39	
	4	1,0072	0,138		3,43	
	5	1,0040	0,136		3,39	

Through the results of the study, which was conducted five times, it was found that the content of anthraquinone derivatives in the roots of the Rheum palaestinum Feinbrun by plant by colorimetric method ranges between 3.37-3.48% In Table 1

Experience has shown that this method is reliable, accurate and simple; perform compared to previously mentioned methods. However, it is not suitable for determining the quantity of individual anthracene derivatives with sufficient accuracy.

Our current study is similar to study [5], which was conducted on the roots of the Rheum palaestinum Feinbrun by spread in Syria, except that our study differs from it in the place of collecting the study samples, as they were collected in Jordan, and it differs in the method of determining the quantity of anthraquinone derivatives, as the researcher used the (UV-vis spectrophotometric method) method, and we used in our research the (colorimetric) method.

The Value of Study

This research is important for several reasons:

1. Because it shows the results of a study of a rare plant that is threatened with extinction due to the actions of some, which is the Palestinian rhubarb plant, which belongs to the family (Polygonaceae), in terms of the amount of anthraquinone derivatives in its roots.
2. Use the colorimetric method to determine the amount of anthraquinone derivatives in Palestinian rhubarb roots
3. The lack of chemical studies on Palestinian rhubarb to the point of nonexistence.

Recommendations

Chemical researchers in general and botanists in particular must focus on searching for the effective components in these plants, especially Palestinian rhubarb, and try to isolate and identify them and learn about their therapeutic effects if Palestinian plants are to be useful in both matters, traditional and modern medicine.

Conclusions

This paper deals with the determination of the amount of anthraquinone by colorimetric method in the root of *Rheum palaestinum* Feinbrun.

According to the results of a study conducted to confirm the concentration of anthraquinone derivatives in the roots, the roots contain (3.41%).

The results of the study showed that while the colorimetric method is believed to be reliable, accurate, easy to use and less expensive than alternative methods, it is not suitable for accurate quantitation of certain individual anthracene derivatives.

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